

Is Tribal Development Possible for Adivasis Communities ? Revisiting Dams, Policies, Programs, & Projects : A Cases from Western Odisha

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Abstract :- Adivasis communities have been witnessing a plethora of discrimination, humiliation, and exclusion in the name of tribal development, policies, projects, and programs. They are replaced, displaced, and rehabilitated where they are not interested and forced to stay. In such conditions, they are affected severely by basic needs and wants. They are exploited socio-culturally, economically, and politically; they are excluded when they are with mainstreaming and included when they are with ethnocentrism. Thus, circumstances led their formal identities loose and later identities gain as no one. The study is specifically based on a field visit, observation, informal interview, case study, and secondary source of data. Again study includes multi-sited areas for the study of Adivasis communities to know their social, cultural, political, and economic exclusion; such exclusion brings different kinds of marginality among Adivasis communities. The study also sees the overall development of Adivasis after the displacement, and rehabilitation from original place and resident, and it reveals that it is not helping them in their holistic life as Adivasis rather as mainstreaming. Sociologically, the study includes the emic and etic perspectives to know their social, cultural, religious, livelihood, economy, and others aspects of life. The study is going to explore Rengali Dam, Hirakud Dam, Kansbahal Dam, Pitamahal Dam, Gohira Dam, Mandira Dam, and Dadraghati Dam others to know how Adivasis are marginalized and exploited. They are vulnerable to different laws, policies, programs, and projects by different NGOs both national and international, and government steps. Thus, the study is broadly looking at "Is tribal development possible for Adivasis Communities?"

Keywords :- Tribal Development, Adivasis Communities, Dams, Projects, Programs, Western Odisha.

Introduction :- Odisha occupies a unique position among the Indian States and Union Territories for having a rich and colorful tribal Scenario. Majorities of scheduled tribes or Adivasis live in hilly and forest regions. Their economy is largely subsistence-oriented, non-stratified, and non-specialized. Their social structure is simple and aspirational and their needs are not many, they live a simple life. Though the STs or Adivasis in Odisha have suffered from social, educational, and economic backwardness due to geo-historical reasons they are strong in their way (Xaxa, 2014). Thus, they have their distinctiveness and social-cultural milieu. The development of Adivasis in Odisha is seen after the independence, their socio-economic and healthcare developed very lately. However, it has picked up momentum but yet this category lag behind compared to others. Even if we cannot say, that Adivasis in Odisha are developed, it is because there are certain spheres of life where they are none- such as education, health, agriculture, and other aspects.

In Odisha, we have 62 tribal communities that speak as many as 74 dialects and more who are spread over 30 districts and 314 blocks (Chandramouli, C., & General, R., 2011). They have their ethos, ideology, worldview, value-orientations, and cultural heritage that are rich and varied. At one end of the scale there are nomadic food gathers and hunters and at the other end, skilled settled agriculturalists and horticulturalists. Thus, tribal areas of Odisha, are present an extremely diverse socio-economic panorama. Geographically, Odisha is full of mineral resources, raw materials, and iron ore and those are present where Adivasis or scheduled tribes are residing. As per the Census of India 2011, the state of Odisha has the third-highest percentage of tribal population in the country which stands at 9590756. They constitute 22.85% of the total

population of the state and contribute 9.17% to the total tribal population of the country (Pothal & Panda, 2017).

Research Questions/Objectives :- While discussing tribal development in India- policies, and programs – it is obvious question comes – is tribal development possible for Adivasis communities or is it just in the name of Adivasis- different policies, projects, schemes, programs, dams, zoo, and SEZs (Special Economic Zones) are made – need to ponder and introspect critically? After the government of India, the constitution of India, DPSP (Directive Principle of State Policy), Human rights, articles and there are many forms of rules and regulations those are made to protect, safeguard, provide security, preserve, conserve, and many others – but why do tribal or Adivasis always lag compare to mainstream society. Why Adivasis or STs are considered to be backward, marginalize, savage, uncivilized; why they are discriminated against, humiliated, exploited, and stigmatized by mainstream society.

Questioning the plethora of subjects related to Adivasis or STs – the study interrogates and introspects the tribal development and rise some research objectives. Firstly to study the marginality and vulnerability of Adivasis communities. Secondly, to study the different multi-sited regions specifically developmental projects like dams to know their social, cultural, religious, political, livelihood, education, and health status of Adivasis communities. Thirdly, to study the different problems and issues of the tribes such as cultural, social, religious, economic, education, health, and the problem of geographical isolation. Fourthly, to revisit the measures taken for the upliftment of scheduled tribes such as the policy of isolation, the policy of assimilation, and the policy of integration. Fifthly, to know the different tribal welfare activities such as constitutional safeguard, economic facilities, educational facilities, medical facilities, tribal research, the role of voluntary organization, and five-year plans.

Methods and Techniques used for the Study :- The study mainly focused on Marginalized and

Vulnerable communities- They are Scheduled Tribes or Adivasis Communities. Since they are marginalized social class – government or state, policymakers, and others target them- they encroach their Jal, jungle, and Jamin (water, forest, and land). Governments and others decide to take away their land in the name of development of tribe, use their land for the various purpose (dams, projects, garden, Zoo, SEZs, different institutions like education, hospital, and government office). Thus, they have abandoned their rights over land, forest, and water (which are cosmos for them, life for them, and livelihood for them, protector, safeguard, and security for them). As a result, these uncertainty and unpredictable occurrences, challenge Adivasis like – challenging their life cycle, their marriage, culture, identity, custom, health, education, and tradition. They were challenged with their agricultural setup, marketing, forest produced and livelihood. To know their vulnerability, marginality, and challenge in the name of tribal development in western Odisha. The study follows field visits to see the places (Rengali Dam, Hirakud Dam, Kansbahal Dam, Gohira Dam, Mandira Dam, and Dadraghati Dam, and others). Use a technique of informal interview with the officer, staff, locals, displaced Adivasis. Observation technique is used to see the local and displaced, and rehabilitated Adivasis communities to know their way of life. In-depth interview technique is used to collect information from Adivasis – how their land, forest, and water (as their rights over it) are taken away by governments or state for public use after which – how they have become vulnerable and marginal in the society.

Approach to Study Tribal Development :- We have seen looking different approaches, views, frameworks, and perspectives in examining, elaborating, interrogating, and understanding the Adivasis and development. In the social science discipline and specifically in sociology the aspects of Emic & Etic are new perspectives or approaches to studying the society, culture, group, communities, and individual to know the behavior, socio-cultural settings, development, growth,

cultural lag, and other aspects. Hence, here Emic is from within the social group or from Adivasis themselves (from the perspective of the subject), Etic is from outside of the mainstream society what they say about tribal development or Adivasis backwardness (from the perspective of the observer). Thus, it provides how one can observe and analyze things happening around in a point of view as insider and outsider (Morris et al., 1999). This perspective is used to study the marginalized and vulnerable social, religious groups; and it throws lights from both sides (Spiers, 2000). This approach/perspectives/framework/view helps the researcher understand the subject matter better. The terms Etic/Emic were coined by linguist Kenneth Pike who argued that the tools developed for describing linguistic behaviors could be adapted to the description of any human social behavior. But it can't be limited to this alone rather it provides more explanation and meaning to it in quality and quantity – how they are marginalized and vulnerable in society (Niblo & Jackson, 2004)

Adivasis Marginality and Vulnerability :- Every society goes through some kinds of torture, exploitation, humiliation, and marginalization. These are some forms that indicate the Adivasis marginality and vulnerability. Such unpleasant tastes are seen among not only Adivasis but it is seen among different religious, cultural, social, caste and class groups. The above groups can be structurally stratified into two operational ways; such as majority and minority. Majority groups always enjoy the rank, prestige, and status of the society because of their majoritarian strength, literacy, development, and growth. But minority groups are always vulnerable and marginalized in different ways, such as economic, social, religious, political, education, health, literacy, education, and others. Thus, these social and religious groups are also exploited, humiliated, stigmatized, and discriminated against by mainstream society. These minorities are SCs, STs, OBCs, and SEBC (socially and economically backward caste) as social, economic, and political category/ there are religious minorities as well such as Muslims,

Christians, Buddhists, Parsis, Sikhs, and Jains. Looking at their marginality and vulnerability – governments or states take an opportunity to make different policy measures like projects, dams, SEZs (special economic zones), botanical gardens, Zoo, programs, and schemes.

The elaborative way – Adivasis marginality and vulnerability could be seen from their way of life. As they are staying in geographically isolated places such as hilly regions, over the mountain areas, near river belts, and in a forest area. They are separated from mainstream society – it indicates that Adivasis are away from social, and cultural assimilation. They are rarely integrated with the civilized society as many scholars and academicians would say – such as education, economy, health, and polity. They are marginalized on their living standard of life, missing out on the modern system of education, learning, skills, and training; drawing drinking water from a faraway place such as from river, stream, or small dug well by themselves. Thus, they face problems with water scarcity during summer and get dirty drinking water in the rainy season. Hence, this kinds of situation deteriorate their health when they drink unhygienic drinking water and get numerous virus and illness. They also do not have proper pakka housing – they make their housing from stubble and chaff. They do practice simple semi-permanent agriculture that becomes their subsistence and self-sufficiency. A study was done by Jean Dreze (2015) about a marginalized tribe that lives in hamlets of misery and despair. In his elaboration, it is huddled in tiny huts and they are haunted by hunger and illness.

Adivasis as Marginalized Class/Group/Community :- Adivasis itself tells about collective or group of people –when they are in a group, there is group consciousness and we-feeling among them, they live in a specific geographical area, have social equality among themselves, they have common thinking, customs, traditions, belief, and worship. They always do things in common, they are not isolated. But their development, growth, and mobility are measured they are

mostly backward in many ways- such as social, economic, and education; thus they are called marginalized social groups. According to the Constitution of India, they are known as Scheduled Tribes. They called as Adivasis. According to caste stratification, they fall out in the system; from ancient times they have isolated themselves and stayed in hilly, mountain, jungle, and river beds. As we know, Indian Society is socially stratified in a top-down manner which reveals the inequality in the society, and Adivasis are the vulnerable and marginal community who are totally out of the system. From ancient times, this group of people is a marginalized class who are socially, economically, and educationally backward. Thus they are illiterate, unaware of education, poverty-ridden, exploited, and untouchable. Adivasis are the second larger backward marginalized community in Indian society. They are mostly seen in Odisha, Bihar, and Madhya Pradesh. Adivasis are known in different names – banbasi, adimjati, banjati, adim adivasi. Ghurye (1943) calls them 'Backward Hindu' which many tribal ethnic groups do not accept, they believe that they are not Hindus, they are separate and have a special identity which makes them Adivasis, Gandhiji would call them 'Girijan'.

Discussion on Tribal Development & Analysis :-

Tribal development is a scholarly term used by many academicians, policymakers, governments, agencies, and scholars to explain and elaborate the growth and mobility of a specific community, group, and class. In the name of development, we have seen different problems and issues with regards to Adivasis land, forest, and mineral – Adivasis are denied the rights of their jal, jungle, and Jamin (Padel, 2012). As Felix would say, it is the government that makes policies for the Adivasis and secure their life, land, jal, and jungle. It is the constitutional provision for the Adivasis that strengthens the community as identical. Again it is the policy of isolation, assimilation, and integration that makes more changes in the Adivasis communities and they impact severely (Singh, 1982; Xaxa, 1999). The tribal development should be proper and effective when it is made by

the Adivasis for the Adivasis and of the Adivasis; development of Adivasis should not be business or abrupt, it should be slow and gradual that uses protective discrimination (Xaxa, 2001).

- a. **Hirakud Dam :-** It is constructed across the Mahanadi River which extent to 15 km in the Sambalpur district of Odisha. The dam also extends a lake, Hirakud Reservoir for 55Km. The determination of constructing this dam is to regulate the interrupted droughts of lower delta regions where floods may destruct crops and channelize the water through the canal system, produce hydroelectricity through hydroelectric plants, industrial use, and use for irrigation of land. But issues are here gradually the storage capacity of the dam is dipping, there are water conflicts between nearby districts, farmers protest for not getting water for farming (Nayak, 2010). Lost temples (more than 200), cattle (wild animals), hills, villages, loss of wildlife, people are affected by the dam construction. The dam mostly affected the native of the western part of Odisha specifically the Adivasis community who were nearly 150,000 people and 22,000 families. The loss of human existence in Hirakud dam was compensated by providing the amount of US \$ 150 million in 2019 but after revision, the amount reduced to the US \$ 120 million in 2019, and reality compensation paid to the people was US \$ 43 million in 2019. Thus, it shows –where the development of tribes, Adivasis, or other communities? The question remains unanswered.
- b. **Rengali Dam :-** It is located in Odisha, India. Constructed across the Brahmani River in Rengali Village, located 70 km away from Angul district of Odisha. Rengali Dam is spread out to 70.5 m tall and 1040 m wide. It is the second-largest reservoir in Odisha. It has a catchment area of 25,250 km square that is mostly forests and wasteland. The purpose of constructing the dam was to generate electricity and provide irrigation facilities. The dam was constructed in 1985, the project was

not welcomed by local people during the conception and initial implementation of the project due to the displacement of several people and the way the government tackled the issue. The project has displaced a total of 10,700 families according to the report but there were more families. This Rengali village was a tribal belt where mostly Adivasis were there who are mostly isolated from the mainstream society who were residing nearby by Brahmani river belt. The Dam has affected the environment, humans, animals, villages, and others severely.

- c. **Kansbahal-Pitamahal-Mandira Dams** :- These three dams are located in the Sundargarh district of western Odisha. These dams are constructed to provide water irrigation for land, industrial use, and water supply for towns and villages. These three dams also encroached the land of Adivasis who are marginalized and vulnerable for public use Adivasis were displaced and rehabilitated. They are supposed to be compensated in the form of money, employment opportunity, housing, education, and health. But some have got it and some are denied.
- d. **Gohira & Dadraghati Dams** :- Likewise, we have also Gohira Dam in Deogarh district of Reamal block in Odisha, Dadraghati Dam in Dhenkanal district of Odisha. These two dams are mostly constructed for the irrigation of land through a canal system. These two dams are also located in tribal regions, they are also not compensated as is promised by the authorities. They are now vulnerable and marginalized in many ways –social, cultural, educational, economic, political. They have lost their livelihood, way of life, pattern of custom, tradition, belief, and practices. They have lost their rights over land, water, and forests. Thus, it simply tells about how in the name of tribal development Adivasis communities are used, exploited, displaced, and rehabilitated in vulnerable and marginalized conditions.

Conclusion :- As we know Adivasis communities are the prime concerned for the development of India; thus, they should have a special concern for the group- in terms of health, education, employment opportunities, and reservation process – although all special concerns are there it is not utilized properly and not implemented according to the constitution of India and government prescription. When any projects, policies, programs, and schemes are making or implementing prior concerns should be taken in the decision-making process of the Adivasis communities. The proper measures should be taken for the upliftment of scheduled tribes or Adivasis communities such as the policy of isolation, the policy of assimilation, and the policy of integration. It should not be forced on them, or make a policy, program, project, and scheme from a top-down or bottom-up approach rather it should be a mixed approach. The reservation policy in job and education should be proper and implement without any biases. The tribal research center should be implemented to find out the Adivasis community and their socio-cultural, education, and health status. As these communities are backward, uncivilized, barbaric, savage, and illiterate as mainstream say – so, they should be given more attention, education, care, and love for the betterment and improvement of Adivasis communities. Looking at their lifestyle and backwardness – they should not be humiliated, exploited, stigmatized, and forced to do anything without their interest. Mainstream society should treat them as their brother and sister, and Indian.

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